

About the relevance of anion- π interactions in water

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Anion- π interactions are emerging as an exotic feature with potential applications in chemistry. In the last years its relevance in living systems has been outlined so far there is not any concluding significant evidence about the participation of anion- π interactions in the recognition event in water, as long as anion- π sensors contain large aromatic hydrophobic surfaces with limited solubility. By transforming a neutral heterocycle (quinoline for example) into its corresponding salt (quinolinium) we have been able to overcome solubility issues and new cationic water soluble fluorophores have been prepared. Herein we use *N*-alkylated heterocycles as π -acidic surfaces to shed light on the nature of anion- π in water by direct measurement of the fluorescence and UV/vis spectra in combination with DFT and X-ray analyses.

Introduction

Anion- π interactions have exponentially gained interest during the last three decades.^[1] Beginning with pioneering existence postulated in the gas phase,^[2] a series of researches devoted to the design of molecular structures able to show, quantify and employ these exotic interactions were initiated.^[3] Today anion- π interactions are vastly reported in the literature even as a tool in catalysis.^[4] Thus, this interaction type has been proved extremely significant in the design of functional molecules and also relevant in living systems.^[3a,5] However, the studies that are able to identify anion- π interactions in water are scarce due to solubility issues associated with the aromatic ligands employed.^[1,6a-b] Acetonitrile or DMSO are appropriate solvents for these studies, however they dramatically differ from the natural aqueous medium as recent results with tetrazine-based receptors indicate.^[6c-d] Herein we explore the possibility of creating water soluble polyaromatic receptors to shed light on how significant this interaction can be in pure water. Molecules with π -acidic surfaces are receptors particularly prone to display anion- π interactions because of their positive Q_{zz} tensor values.^[4a] Arenes with withdrawing groups are very much used to this purpose (i.e. hexafluorebenzene $Q_{zz} = +9.5$ B or 1,3,5-trinitrobenzene $Q_{zz} = +20$ B). Such induced dipole values yield aromatic surfaces where anions can bond. In order to conceive π -acidic surfaces we explored the idea of alkylating nitrogen based heterocycles (Figure 1, Figure 2 top). Similar molecules to compound **1** (bearing quinolinium moieties) had already been proposed as excellent anion fluorescent chemosensors.^[7] Specifically, some quinolinium derivatives have proved ideal for

the quantification of these interactions by NMR or UV/Vis in organic solvents.^[7a]

Figure 1. Heterocycles selected for the study of anion- π interactions and surface potential calculation showing significant changes upon alkylation.

Results and discussion

Target compounds **1**, **2** and **3** (Figure 2) were obtained as bromide salts by mixing tribromobenzene **4** with the corresponding heterocycle **5a-c** in presence of DMF. The π acidity of the initial compounds (**5a-c**) was evaluated by DFT calculations. Even though **1-3** have negative Q_{zz} values (figure 2, middle) non ideal for anion- π interactions, dramatic changes in the surface potential calculations were observed after alkylation (figure 1 for model compound **3a** and reagent **5c**, SI). Indeed, the calculations show acidic surfaces (deep blue color) for all the alkylated compounds (See SI S4 for all surface potential calculations). On the other hand, the presence of three positive charges ensures high water solubility for these compounds

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Figure 2. Selected compounds (top). Q_{zz} values for starting reagents (middle) and general reaction conditions (bottom).

Crystals suitable for x-ray diffraction analysis were obtained by slow evaporation of methanol solutions containing **1-3**. The x-ray analysis confirmed not only that compounds **1,2,3** bear three heterocycles, but also the alkylation position in the precursor triazole derivatives **5b** and **5c**. In all cases, bromide appears as counter anion (figure 3a-c). In **1** there are three bromide anions interacting with positively charged quinolinium moieties from different molecules.

The closest distance of Br1 with an aromatic carbon atom 3.564(5) Å (Br1-C21) corresponds practically to the sum of Van der Waals radii. Such distance may be ascribed to an anion- π interaction in the solid state.^[1a,8] The quinolinium units form π stacks of 6 members. In the two ends of the stack there is a bromide anion (Br1) placed very close to the aromatic moiety (see SI: S3). In **2**, the bromide anions are located over each triazole ring of the aromatic unit. The shortest distance is 3.319 Å, from Br3 to the centroid of the nearby triazole ring. In this case, the shortest interatomic distance is 3.302(6) Å (Br3- N7) and it is 3% shorter than the sum of their van der Waals radii. In **3**, two of the triazoloquinolinium units of each molecule are forming π stacks with units of other molecules. The third unit interacts with one bromide anion (Br2) that is placed close to the π acidic surface of the triazoloquinolinium unit, being the shortest distance 3.461(5) Å (Br2- C31) The distance is 3% shorter than sum of van der Waals radii. The values of the observed distances are within the range established as an evidence of anion- π interaction (distance < 3.70 Å).^[1a,8] Even though solid state and solution structures may be very different in these case, the values of the distances measured suggest that these interactions may hold also in solution.

Figure 3. a) ORTEP representation of **1**, b) ORTEP representation of **2**, green dot represents the centre of the triazole ring b) ORTEP representation of **3**, d) Emission spectra of **1** (red), **2** (blue) and **3** (black) recorded in 10^{-4} M water solutions, e) Theoretical Energy profile (Scan B3LYP/6-31G** in H_2O) approaching bromide towards the centre of 5 membered ring in **3a**, f) Theoretical surface energy calculated (B3LYP/6-31G**) by moving bromide through x and y axis at a fixed z distance

Theoretical calculations were performed for **3** (B3LYP/6-31G**) using water as solvent figures 3e and 3f).^[9] Figure 3e shows the energy profile obtained when a bromide anion approaches the centroid of a five-membered ring in compound **3a**. In agreement with x-ray data, bromide showed a bonding distance of around 3.6 Å. In addition, when modeling the stabilization of bromide through the y/x plane (figure 3f) at a fixed z distance, the minimum energy was once again obtained in the centre of the five-membered ring.

Experimental evidences of anion- π interaction in organic solvents solution are well established.^[4,6] For example, quinolinium based receptors exhibit elevated anion sensing features (by fluorescence quenching $\log\beta = 4.7$)^[7a], pyridinium-based receptors also presented high interaction measured by NMR.^[7b] However, fluorescence studies with methyl quinolinium and anions in water revealed weak Stern-Volmer constants according to Verkman.^[7c] This behaviour may be rationalised considering that anion- π interactions are, at least partially, responsible of the quenching phenomena. Compounds **1-3** exhibit intense fluorescence—(figure 4d). Indeed, **1** presented an emission band at 436 nm when excited at 319 nm (See SI) while the triazolium based structures **2** and **3** presented emission bands at 340 and 376 nm, respectively, when excited at 297 nm. Compounds **1** and **3** exhibit large Stokes shift (117 and 78 nm, respectively) while **2** was excited at a secondary absorption band in order to record fluorescence with minimal interference. We anticipated that a large excess of anions may induce fluorescence quenching, and this phenomenon and, thereby, the binding constants could be correlated to the strength of the anion- π interaction in water. Fluorescence quenching was initially evaluated in presence of iodide. As can be seen in figure 4, the emission of **3** decreases upon the addition of iodide. However, the amount of anion required for a significant quenching to occur (50% intensity reduction) was around 120 eq. Around 400 eq. were required to reduce 80% of the signal intensity. For a graphical correlation, in figure 4 (inset) is presented the correlation normalized intensity *versus* iodide equivalents. We note that UV/Vis absorption was measured to ensure that no absorption changes in the excitation wavelength appeared upon the addition of anions

Figure 4. Fluorescence titration of **3** with iodide.

For an accurate measurement, 10^{-5} M water solutions of **1-3** were titrated with concentrated TBAI solution (0.05 M). This allowed to keep a relative constant total volume. Fluorescence quenching was observed for all compounds **1-3** in presence of iodide. Analogous titrations were performed with other anions. Employing Stern-Volmer plots, linear correlations were observed (See SI S6). The K_{SV} values obtained from the titrations are presented in Table 1. Halides, nitrate, nitrite, acetate and phosphate were selected as relevant anions for this study. Milli Q water was employed for the preparation of ligand solutions (10^{-5} M) instead of a buffered solution to avoid any anion interference. For all solutions, pH measurements afforded values close to 5.4. Upon the titration, pH variation did not afford a value able to either protonate or deprotonate the ligands. The lower measured pH was observed with phosphate solution (pH = 3.9) and the higher value with iodide (pH = 7.5) (See SI).

Table 1. Stern-Volmer K_{SV} (M^{-1}) constants for anion titrations.[a]

Anion	1	2	3
Iodide	483	109	520
Bromide	370	43	287
Chloride	248	< 10.	14
Fluoride	< 10	< 10.	< 10
Nitrate	< 10	76	14
Nitrite	330	216	428
Phosphate	< 10	42	< 10.
Acetate	78	203	73

[a] Linear model was employed: $I_0/I = 1 + [Anion]K_{SV}$

Results obtained with halide family show that iodide is the most efficient quencher. Fluoride induced almost no quenching in any compound. Normally in organic solvents the order is the contrary.^[6a,7a,10] However, it must be taken into account that water solvation is more efficient with small halogens. For an efficient anion- π interaction to occur, the anion must be naked, solvating molecules must be, at least, partly removed. Contrarily to what happens in organic solvents where larger anions are more efficiently solvated, fluoride is very efficiently solvated in water. The high hydration of fluoride along with its non-polarizability makes fluoride to interact very poorly with these extended aromatic surfaces in water. This result is in agreement with previously published results obtained in water for diazine-based receptors.^[6c-d] It is important to note, that compounds **1,2** and **3** present three positive charges that must assist on the formation of the anion- π bond, by means of electrostatic interactions; even with this benefit, observed values are low.

It is relevant to point out that **1** makes small differences between I⁻, Br⁻ or Cl⁻ (in terms of magnitude, Table 1 first

column). On the other hand, **2**, and more remarkably **3**, present clear differences in the values of the constants.^[11] We propose here that a larger polarizability is in the basis of these differences; **3** has 14 π electrons while **1** has 10 π electrons. Globally, these experiences afforded K_{SV} values < 650. With similar systems in organic solvents, in the literature, the values reported include 2:1 stoichiometry (ligand:anion) with $K > 50000$ measured by NMR.^[7a] The quenching efficiency of nitrite is much greater than that of nitrate, in particular ligands **1** and **3** present an almost two orders of magnitude difference. Phosphate did not produce any effect at all. Acetate quenched all systems. It is important to remark that K_{SV} constants of *ca.* 10 indicate that no significant interaction occurs.

While addition of halide anions provides neither significant changes in the UV-Vis spectra nor the appearance of charge transfer bands, addition of nitrite or nitrate gives rise to new charge transfer^[12] bands centred at 350-360 nm for nitrite, and at 300 nm for nitrate. However, for observing such a band a larger amount of nitrate has to be added due to its lower quenching efficiency.

Figure 5. UV/Vis titrations of **1** (top) and **3** (bottom) with Nitrite (left) and nitrate (right).

In summary, herein we report on the relative strength of anion- π interaction in water. We have prepared a small family of compounds able to interact with anions. Crystallographic studies afforded distances that are in agreement with the presence of bromide π -surface bonds in all compounds. Fluorescence titration in water afforded quenching phenomena in all cases; however, even though the compounds prepared contain positive charges that can assist the interaction, the calculated K_{SV} constants are small compared to those reported in organic solvents. In the particular case of nitrites and nitrates, charge transfer bands could be observed in the UV/Vis supporting the existence of these weak interactions. These

results clearly outline that anion- π interactions are stronger (and more relevant) in organic solvents or hydrophobic environments, as is the case of the intra membrane space.^[12] However, as water reduces dramatically the strength of this interaction its relevance in living systems may be restricted to hydrophobic environments or other structurally constricted scenarios such is the case of enzymatic sites.^[5b,13]

Experimental

Computational methods:

All calculations were carried out with the Gaussian 09 suite of programs.^[9] Density functional theory^[14] calculations (DFT) have been carried out using the B3LYP^[15] exchange-correlation functionals, together with the standard 6-31G** basis set.^[16] The inclusion of solvent effects has been considered by using a relatively simple self-consistent reaction field (SCRF) method^[17] based on the polarizable continuum model (PCM) of Tomasi's group.^[18] Geometries have been fully optimized with PCM. The solvent we have used was water.

Synthesis of new compounds:

1,1',1''-(benzene-1,3,5-triyltris(methylene))tris(quinolin-1-ium)tribromide (**1**): A solution of 1,3,5-tris(bromomethyl) benzene (**4**, 0.5 mmol), quinoline (**5a**, 5 mL) in dimethyl formamide (10 mL) was stirred at 25 °C for 8 h. During this time, a white precipitate appeared. The remaining organic solvent was removed and the solid was washed 3 times with DMF and 3 times with ethyl acetate. The solid was dried overnight under vacuum affording **1** as a white powder (207 mg, 55%) M.P. 213-217 °C. ¹H NMR (300 MHz, MeOD-*d*₄) δ 9.56 (dd, $J = 5.9, 1.3$ Hz, 3H), 9.26 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 3H), 8.52-8.37 (m, 3H), 8.32-8.20 (m, 3H), 8.20-8.08 (m, 3H), 8.08-7.88 (m, 6H), 7.32 (s, 3H), 6.34 (s, 6H). ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, MeOD-*d*₄) δ 151.54(CH), 149.95(CH), 139.25(C), 137.42(CH), 137.26(C), 132.28(CH), 131.75(C), 131.52(CH), 128.06(CH), 123.44(CH), 120.15(CH), 61.12(CH₂). IR (ATR) :3382, 3068, 2960, 1627, 1560, 1528, 1470, 1368, 1296, 1142 cm⁻¹. HRMS (ESI-TOF) m/z Calcd. for C₃₆H₂₉N₃ [M-1]²⁺ 251.6180, Found 251.6176.

1,1',1''-(benzene-1,3,5-triyltris(methylene))tris(3-methyl-[1,2,3]triazolo [1,5-*a*]pyridin-2-ium)tribromide (**2**): 3-methyl-[1,2,3]triazolo[1,5-*a*]pyridin (**5b**, 5 mmol) and 1,3,5-tris(bromomethyl) benzene (**4**, 0.5 mmol) were mixed in dimethyl formamide (2 mL) and heated at 80 °C during 8 h. After this time a white precipitated appeared. The remaining liquid phase was removed, and the precipitated was washed 3 times with DMF and 3 times with ethyl acetate. Solid was dried overnight under vacuum affording **2** as a white powder. (280 mg, 74%) M.P. 210 decomp. ¹H NMR (300 MHz, MeOD-*d*₄) δ 9.09 (dt, $J = 6.9, 1.0$ Hz, 3H), 8.32 (dt, $J = 9.0, 1.3$ Hz, 3H), 7.94 - 7.60 (m, 9H), 6.10 (s, 6H), 2.88 (s, 9H). ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, MeOD-*d*₄) δ 136.05(C), 135.58(C), 134.99(C), 134.86(C), 131.42(CH), 130.52(CH), 127.17(CH), 124.23(CH), 120.82 (CH), 55.10 (CH₂), 9.34 (CH₃). IR (ATR) :3410, 3002, 25968, 2916, 1645, 1610, 1435,

1397, 1154 cm^{-1} . HRMS (ESI-TOF) m/z Calcd. For $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_9$ $[\text{M}]^{3+}$ 172.0869, Found 172.0874, for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{29}\text{N}_9$ $[\text{M}-1]^{2+}$ 257.6268, Found 257.6280.

1,1',1''-(benzene-1,3,5-triyltris(methylene))tris([1,2,3]triazolo[1,5-*a*]quinolin-2-ium)tribromide (**3**): [1,2,3]Triazolo[1,5-*a*]quinoline (**5c**, 5 mmol) and 1,3,5-tris(bromomethyl) benzene (**4**, 0.5 mmol) were mixed in dimethyl formamide (2 mL) and heated at 80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ during 8 h. After this time, a white precipitated appeared. The remaining liquid phase was removed, and the precipitated wash washed 3 times with DMF and 3 times with ethyl acetate. Solid was dried overnight under vacuum affording **2** as a white powder (312, 72%). M.P. 194-196. ^1H NMR (300 MHz, MeOD-d_4) δ 9.5(s, deuterated 3H/3D), 8.72 (dd, $J = 7.1, 2.6$ Hz, 3H), 8.25-8.22 (m, 6H), 8.08-7.96 (m, 12H), 6.30 (s, 6H). ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, MeOD-d_4) δ 137.13(C), 136.85(C), 136.12(C), 134.62(CH), 133.33(CH), 133.20(CH), 132.80(CH), 132.63(C), 132.08(CH), 131.17(CH), 117.79(CH), 115.51(CH), 58.07(CH_2). IR (ATR) :3418, 3069, 3012, 2937, 1627, 1611, 1559, 1470, 1449, 1296, 1225, 1191 cm^{-1} . HRMS (ESI-TOF) m/z Calcd. for $\text{C}_{39}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_9$ $[\text{M}]^{3+}$ 208.0869, Found 208.0871, for $\text{C}_{39}\text{H}_{29}\text{N}_9$ $[\text{M}-1]^{2+}$ 311.6265, Found 311.6274.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare

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